

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Extensification of cultivation practices promotes earthworm populations

In a field trial during four consecutive growing seasons, an intensive (rotating tillage, intensive fertilization, fallow in between cultivations) and an extensive cropping system (reduced tillage, extensive fertilization, cover crops in between cultivations) were compared and this within both a conventional and an organic cropping system. During this period the crops were leek, celery, cauliflower and roman lettuce. In three out of the four years, earthworms in the soil were sampled. This was done by identifying the earthworm in samples of 25 x 25 x 25 cm³ of soil in four replications for each cropping system.

During three years of sampling there were always more earthworms present in the extensively cultivated plots compared to the intensively cultivated plots in both the conventionally managed field and the organic field. For all treatments there

was an increasing trend throughout the years. If the extensive cultivation of the plots caused an increase in earthworm populations, this may have influenced the populations in the intensively cultivated plots, as they are located close to each other.

In this trial we did not observe a reduction in soil bulk density, but this effect of earthworms is widely accepted in literature. The trial period may have been too short to show this long term effect. Other positive effects of more earthworms in the soil are better drainage, faster decomposition of organic material and much more. This trial showed that a more extensive cropping system and especially reduced tillage can help to promote earthworm populations.

1. Soil samples were taken from 25 x 25 x 25 cm of soil

2. Earthworms were counted on the field

KEYWORDS

Earthworms, extensive cultivation

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